

APPLICATION OF THE FINITE-DIFFERENCE METHOD TO THE ANALYSIS OF DYNAMIC BEHAVIOUR OF COMPOSITE RODS

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SUMMARY: This study implements the first order explicit finite-difference scheme to the numerical analysis of the composite rod of finite length subjected to the impact loading. The general methodology is outlined for the dynamic analysis of the rod that has the varying along its length dimensions of the cross-section and mechanical properties of the material. Both, the size of the cross-section and axial modulus of elasticity are also considered as time-dependent functions. The proposed approach provides the capability to take into account the possible changes of these functions during the computational process. The effectiveness of the analysis is demonstrated using a particular example. The calculated deformations of the rod are presented for a few selected instants of time. Numerical results are verified by comparison with the closed form solution.

KEYWORDS: composite rod, dynamics, numerical analysis, explicit finite-difference method.

INTRODUCTION

Dynamic numerical analysis of the composite rod is considered in the paper. The computational algorithm is based on the implementation of the grid-characteristic explicit finite-difference scheme. The composite rod is subjected to the axial impact load that may be modelled by appropriate boundary conditions. The solution algorithm is designed to take into account possible physical elastic nonlinearity of the rod's material and change in the cross-sectional dimensions. Application of the computational procedure to the dynamic analysis of the rod loaded at one end with instantaneously applied constant force has been undertaken and results were compared with the analytical solution.

GRID-CHARACTERISTIC EXPLICIT SCHEME

Consider a continuous cantilever composite elastic rod, which has acting at the end boundary a time-dependent force. The resulting equation of motion is presented as follows:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(A(x,t)E(x,t) \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right) = \rho A(x,t) \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} . \quad (1)$$

Here, x is an axial co-ordinate, t is time, $u = u(x,t)$ is the displacement of a point of the rod with the axial co-ordinate x at the moment t , ρ is the density of the rod's material, $A(x,t)$ is the area of the cross-section and $E(x,t)$ is Young's modulus of the rod's material at this point.

The rod has a length l and the origin of the axis x is placed at the left-hand rod's end. At the initial moment of time, rod's points may be under deformation of compression or tension. These points may also move with some initial velocities. According to this, the following initial conditions could be imposed on the rod's displacements and initial velocities:

$$u(x,t)|_{t=0} = u(x,0) = f(x), \quad \left. \frac{\partial u(x,t)}{\partial t} \right|_{t=0} = h(x),$$

where $f(x)$ and $h(x)$ are some given functions.

In the case when there are no deformations and no displacements of the rod's cross-sections at the initial moment of time $t = 0$, the initial conditions are presented by the following equations:

$$u(x,t)|_{t=0} = u(x,0) = 0, \quad \left. \frac{\partial u(x,t)}{\partial t} \right|_{t=0} = 0 .$$

It is assumed that the left-hand side end of the rod is fixed and coincides with the origin of the reference system. The right-hand end of the rod is under the action of a force Q acting axially. In this case, the associated boundary conditions are

$$u(x,t)|_{x=0} = u(0,t) = 0, \quad \left. \frac{\partial u(x,t)}{\partial t} \right|_{x=l} = \frac{Q}{AE} .$$

After differentiation and some rearrangements, the governing equation (1) is presented as follows

$$\rho A \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} - AE \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} = \frac{\partial(AE)}{\partial x} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} . \quad (2)$$

In order to convert this equation into dimensionless form, the following dimensionless independent variables are introduced

$$\xi = \frac{x}{l}, \quad \tau = \frac{ct}{l},$$

where $c(x,t) = \sqrt{\frac{E(x,t)}{\rho}}$ is the velocity of propagation of compressive and tensile stress waves.

After some rearrangements, equation (2) becomes

$$\frac{\partial^2 \tilde{u}}{\partial \tau^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{u}}{\partial \xi^2} = \frac{l^2}{\tilde{E}A} \frac{\partial(\tilde{A}\tilde{E})}{\partial \xi} \frac{\partial \tilde{u}}{\partial \xi}, \quad (3)$$

where $\tilde{u}(\xi, \tau) = \frac{u(x, t)}{l}$ is the dimensionless displacement and $\tilde{A}(\xi, \tau) = \frac{A(x, t)}{l^2}$ is the dimensionless cross-sectional area. The dimensionless Young's modulus $\tilde{E}(\xi, \tau) = \frac{E(x, t)}{E^*}$ is the result of division of the dimensional Young's modulus by some parameter E^* .

Introducing the vector-function (vector-column)

$$U(\tau, \xi) = \left\| \frac{\partial \tilde{u}}{\partial \tau}, \frac{\partial \tilde{u}}{\partial \xi}, \tilde{u} \right\|^T = \|U_1, U_2, U_3\|^T,$$

which includes velocities, strains and displacements at any point of the rod at any instant of time, the original equation (3) could be presented in the vector-matrix dimensionless form as follows:

$$\frac{\partial U(\tau, \xi)}{\partial \tau} + B(\tau, \xi, U) \frac{\partial U(\tau, \xi)}{\partial \xi} = F(\tau, \xi, U). \quad (4)$$

Here, the matrix $B(\tau, \xi, U)$ and the vector-column $F(\tau, \xi, U)$ are:

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad F = \begin{bmatrix} F_1 \\ F_2 \\ F_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} l^2 \frac{\partial(\tilde{A}\tilde{E})}{\partial \xi} U_2 \\ 0 \\ U_1 \end{bmatrix}.$$

After rearrangements, the following grid-characteristic scheme suitable for the calculations of the introduced earlier function U could be obtained [1]:

$$U_j^{n+1} = U_j^n + \Delta \tau F_j^n - \frac{\Delta \tau}{2\Delta \xi} \left[(\Omega^{-1} \Lambda \Omega)_{j+\frac{1}{2}}^n (U_{j+1}^n - U_j^n) + (\Omega^{-1} \Lambda \Omega)_{j-\frac{1}{2}}^n (U_j^n - U_{j-1}^n) \right] + \frac{\Delta \tau}{2\Delta \xi} \left[(\Omega^{-1} |\Lambda| \Omega)_{j+\frac{1}{2}}^n (U_{j+1}^n - U_j^n) - (\Omega^{-1} |\Lambda| \Omega)_{j-\frac{1}{2}}^n (U_j^n - U_{j-1}^n) \right].$$

Here, $\Delta \xi$ is the step of integration with respect to axial co-ordinate and $\Delta \tau$ is the step of integration with respect to time. Entries of the diagonal matrix

$$\Lambda = \text{diag} \|\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3\| = \text{diag} \|-1, 1, 0\|$$

are the roots of the characteristic equation

$$\det[B - \lambda I] = 0,$$

where I the unit matrix. The matrix Ω composed of vectors-rows ω^i , $j=1,2,3$, that are determined by the equations

$$\omega^j B = \lambda_j \omega^j, \quad j=1,2,3.$$

The matrix Ω^{-1} is the inverse matrix such that $\Omega\Omega^{-1} = \Omega^{-1}\Omega = I$.

For the case under consideration, these matrices are

$$\Omega = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \Omega^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The proposed algorithm has been applied to the numerical analysis of the composite rod subjected to impact load Q as specified by the boundary conditions. In general case, the proposed procedure is capable to handle the changes of the cross-sectional area and axial modulus of elasticity that would depend on time and axial co-ordinate. The algorithm that would account for the relationship between the modulus of elasticity and cross-sectional area and the value of deformation at any point of the rod at given moment of time could be easily implemented using the finite-difference scheme presented in this Section. In this work, the functionality of the algorithm has been verified on the basis of simplified model, which involved numerical analysis of the composite rod with fixed cross-sectional area and modulus of elasticity. The computational results were compared to the analytical solution in order to demonstrate basic performance of the grid-characteristic scheme at the current stage. In future, more complex examples could be analysed using the described above computational procedure.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

The volume of the numerical data generated as a result of the calculations based on the proposed scheme is so big that they could not be saved neither by the end of the computations nor in the process itself. At the same time, the current values of the process parameters could be calculated for any point of the rod and at any instant of time. The computational program developed in this work provides an opportunity to obtain distributions of the velocities and displacements in time for a few “control” points of the rod, and/or distribution of the velocities and displacements along the rod’s length in some selected instants of time.

As discussed in previous Section, the rod of unit length $\xi \in [0,1]$ with constant cross-sectional area, $\tilde{A}(\xi, \tau) = \text{const}$, and invariable Young’s modulus, $\tilde{E}(\xi, \tau) = \text{const}$, was analysed in order to validate the numerical procedure and demonstrate basic performance of the algorithm (stability and accuracy). The unit length of the rod was subdivided into 150 subintervals. Correspondingly, the step of integration with respect to axial co-ordinate was $\Delta\xi = \frac{1}{150}$. The step of integration with respect to time was determined by the formula

$$\Delta\tau = \text{CFL} \cdot \Delta\xi ,$$

where the Courant – Friedrichs – Lewy (CFL) parameter [2] is the number ranged from 0 to 1.

An axial load of constant value $Q = 5$ (dimensionless units) has been instantaneously applied to the right-hand end of the rod.

The profiles of the waves of deformation at the moment of time $\tau = 0.2$ are shown in Fig. 1 (CFL = 0.2) and in Fig. 2 (CFL = 0.8). It is seen that the solutions obtained are of monotone character.

Fig. 1: Deformation versus axial coordinate ($\tau = 0.2$, CFL = 0.2)

Fig. 2: Deformation versus axial coordinate ($\tau = 0.2$, CFL = 0.8)

The phenomenon of reflection of the wave is shown in Figs 3-4 (CFL = 0.8). Figure 3 corresponds to the moment of time $\tau = 0.8$ (just before the reflection) and Fig. 4 corresponds the moment of time $\tau = 1.2$ (just after the reflection)

Fig. 3: Deformation versus axial coordinate ($\tau = 0.8$, CFL = 0.8)

Fig. 4: Deformation versus axial coordinate ($\tau = 1.2$, CFL = 0.8)

In Figs 1-4, abscissa is represented by the grid points within the closed interval: $\xi \in [0,1]$.

MODEL VALIDATION

Numerical results were compared with the closed form analytical solution of the problem under consideration [3].

For the set of the initial and boundary conditions discussed in previous Sections

$$u|_{t=0} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial t}|_{t=0} = 0, \quad u|_{x=0} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial t}|_{x=l} = \frac{Q}{AE},$$

the analytical formula for the rod's displacement can be obtained in the following form [3]:

$$u(x,t) = \frac{Q}{EA} x - \frac{8Ql}{\pi^2 EA} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n+1)^2} \sin \frac{(2n+1)\pi x}{2l} \cos \frac{(2n+1)\pi ct}{2l}. \quad (5)$$

where, $c = \sqrt{E/\rho}$ is the velocity of propagation of compressive and tensile stress waves.

The rod's deformations have been calculated on the basis of this solution at the moments of time: $\tau = 0.2$, $\tau = 0.8$, and $\tau = 1.2$. The number of terms in the calculation of the sums of the truncated series was $n = 500$. The corresponding results are shown in Figs 5-7. The calculations were also performed with the increased number of retained terms $n = 1000$ and $n = 1500$. The results obtained from these calculations remained the same as for $n = 500$.

Fig. 5: Deformation versus axial coordinate
($\tau = 0.2$)

Fig. 6: Deformation versus axial coordinate
($\tau = 0.8$)

As can be seen, the numerical results are in good agreement with analytical ones. So, the proposed numerical procedure is deemed appropriate in terms of its functionality.

Strictly speaking, analytical results could also be considered as numerical (approximate) since they have been obtained by summation of finite numbers (500, 1000, and 1500) of terms in the series. Approximate analytical solutions are of non-monotone character compared to the numerical ones. They provide closer representation of the step-wise form of the solution.

As for the numerical procedure, it should be noted that the larger value of the parameter CFL provides better approximation of the step function (see Figs. 1-2).

Fig. 7: Deformation versus axial coordinate
($\tau = 1.2$)

CONCLUSION

The computational algorithm developed in this work and based on the implementation of the grid-characteristic explicit finite-difference scheme has a capacity to provide a tool for the numerical analysis of composite rods with varying (in the process of deformation) dimensions of the cross-sections and mechanical properties of the material.

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